

Data and Methodology Pre-publication: A Study of the XXXX Design Process and Participatory Experience

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1 INTRODUCTION

XXX is an hour-long participatory multi-sensory experience that was developed by an interdisciplinary team of researchers, choreographers, artists and technologists including visually impaired and sighted collaborators. XXX combines dance, somatic practices and multi-person VR technologies to create a sensory experience that explores different ways of 'seeing' and 'feeling' across physical, virtual and imagined realities. In this pre-publication document, we set out the methodology for a study that examines recent developments and performances with XXX between 2020-2022.

This document is published as a supplement to a forthcoming study that will examine and discuss the experiences of XXX participants across two workshop sessions with visually impaired participants in XXX (Sep 2021) and twelve performances at the XXX Theatre, XXX (9th-11th May 2022). This document has been published while the interviews were taking place and prior to the analysis of transcripts. In this publication, we describe the data capture and analysis plans. The study was ethically reviewed by XXX's Research Ethics Committee. Following approval, participants were invited to share their thoughts on XXX and their experiences.

2 MOTIVATION

As our role as researchers inherently impacts the qualitative data analysis we perform, we present our motivations.

This study seeks to explore ideas based on the following research questions:

1. How can we define inclusive practice in VR experiences?
2. Can VR be made accessible for visually impaired audiences?
3. How does including audio description in VR performance change the experience of the spectators (i.e. those not wearing a headset)?
4. Is it possible to facilitate a participatory experience / performance with VR technology which offers a cross-modal experience, which does not prioritise the visual sense?
5. What is the process or methodology that can be used to develop inclusive or accessible elements of an experience, not just as add-on features for specific groups, but intrinsic to the aesthetic or design of the piece experienced by everyone?

Working with visually impaired collaborators and participants while developing XXX has opened up questions around how to create inclusive practice with VR technology, particularly how such a currently visual centred technology can be made accessible to visually impaired creators and audiences. This process involved developing auditory representations of the virtual environment to convey virtual interactions and the integration of an audio description layer. The audio description, alongside the crafted one-to-one support and guidance participants (or *travellers*) receive from dancers, the virtual world represented in the VR headset, not only becomes available to people who are visually impaired but also to those who are not in VR. This reaXXXtion led to the development of a *witness* role, which was trialled during the performances at XXX Theatre and which feeds into some of the early premises for XXX. These early ideas centre on "the design and facilitation of VR encounters that expand ideas and expectations of both body and technology" [1] and bring into play the immediate effect of a perceptual tension or *gap* between the visual, virtual environment and the physical, felt environment [2]. Inviting a play and dialogue between the 'inside' of VR and the 'outside', between different sensorial experiences. XXX "calls into question normative bodily-sensorial arrangements with technology and opens up expanded sensory terrain in human-techno relationships" [3].

3 PARTICIPANTS AND INTERVIEWS

The data is drawn from audio recordings of two testing workshop sessions with 6 visually impaired participants (VIPs), and a survey and interviews with a sample of participants from the 96 in total who experienced the final 12 XXX performances at XXX theatre.

3.1 Test Workshop Sessions with VIPs

The workshop participants attended one of two sessions in groups of three where they experienced a work-in-progress showing of XXX before participating in an hour long open ended discussion of their experience with the project team to inform subsequent development of the project.

3.2 XXX Participant Survey and Interviews

35 of the XXX participants completed a survey after the performance. The intention was to also interview participants immediately after the XXX experience at the XXX Theatre; however, for some participants, XXX elicited an emotional response that persisted for some time after the experience had ended. Consequently, participants were instead asked to provide an email address if they would like to participate in a followup interview. All 29 participants who provided email addresses were invited to book a 30 minute video call between the 6th and 26th June 2022, three to six weeks after their experience. All interviews were (or will be) conducted, recorded and transcribed for later analysis by the co-authors. In advance of the interview, participants were (or will be) issued with a comprehensive information pack describing the study. Participants are able to withdraw from the study at any time, while it is active and are asked to provide written consent.

Participants responded to the survey questions, which followed a likert scale, immediately after their experience of the XXX performances at the XXX Theatre.

Please mark on a scale between 1 and 5 your response to the following statements:				
What role did you take in XXX?				
I was a VR traveller		I was a VR witness		
The overall experience was				
5	4	3	2	1
very enjoyable		not enjoyable		
5	4	3	2	1
comfortable		awkward		
My expectations of using Virtual Reality technology were				
5	4	3	2	1
challenged		not challenged/as expected		
I found the experience				
5	4	3	2	1
welcoming/inclusive		not welcoming		
Any information I needed access the experience was				
5	4	3	2	1
available at all times		not available at all		
I was invited to make my own choices through the XXX journey				

Please mark on a scale between 1 and 5 your response to the following statements:				
5	4	3	2	1
strongly agree				strongly disagree
I participated/engaged in the XXX journey				
5	4	3	2	1
fully/as much as possible				hardly/not at all
Please write any further comments here:				

Participants were asked the interview questions below and were free to respond with minimal interaction from the interviewer.

VR technology and sensory perception/modality:
a. Have you experienced VR before? Where / what?
b. Were your expectations of VR technology met / challenged? How / why do you think that is?
c. Did you notice when your attention was inside the VR and when it was outside the VR? Any specific moments you remember?
d. Did you tap into your senses in a different way to usual? How / which senses were involved? Why do you think that was?
Movement, embodiment, and participatory agency:
a. How much did you move through the whole experience? Were there some moments where you moved more / less? Why do you think that was?
b. Did you move as much as you wanted to move, or wanted to move more / less?
c. How much did you feel that you could make choices about how much and how you participated?
On roles - dancer/guide, witness, traveller:
a. What was your sense of / how did you experience the different roles within the piece? I.e. the roles of witness, traveller, and dancer-guide
b. Did you and how did you relate to or connect with the other participants who were Travellers/Witness Did you communicate with one another? How... can you give an example? How did this feel?
c. Did you and how did you relate or connect with the dancer-guides? Did you communicate with the dancer-guides? How... can you give an example? Did you feel supported, invited, challenged etc by the dancer-guides? How ... can you give an example?
Inclusivity and accessibility:
a. Did you feel included throughout the journey? Were there any moments where you didn't? Describe these moments... If you did, what do you think made you feel welcomed, comfortable, included?

VR technology and sensory perception/modality:
<p>b. Did you access all the information you needed to undertake the piece? If no, what was missing?</p> <p>c. Did the voice over giving creative audio description influence your experience of VR (either from inside or outside of the headset)? How? Why do you think that was? Did you and how did you think the audio description added to the experience?</p>
Sound and sonification:
<p>a. What was your experience of sound through the experience?</p> <p>b. Could you hear different layers of sound? Can you describe them? Which layers of sound worked well for you and why?</p> <p>c. Was the sound located in certain parts of the space? If yes, can you explain more about your experience of the spatial element of the sound?</p>
Transformation, before and after:
<p>a. Did you feel differently after the experience to how you had felt on arriving at the theatre? Can you describe this change?</p>
Anything else you want to say?

4 ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In this study analysis will take a phenomenological approach, exploring the personal experiences of participants. Because of its fit with an inductive approach and its capacity to create a rich and nuanced view of these interviews, Braun and Clarke's framework [4] reflexive thematic analysis has been selected as the methodology for analysis. This study focuses on using a reflexive approach for analysis [5], exploring the perspectives of participants in an approach Alvesson, Hardy and Harley describe as multi-perspective practices. Notably, we anticipate a varied set of experiences and perspectives to be captured from which this study aims to draw out ideas. The analysis will examine the responses inductively, intending to explore the explicit semantic concepts introduced by participants, though consideration will also be given to latent, underlying meaning where relevant. In line with Braun and Clarke's [6] description of reflexive thematic analysis, we recognise that as researchers we play an active role in the generation of qualitative information [7]. To support this we also provide a descriptive background of the researchers taking part in this study at the end of this publication, aiming to make clear some of our perspectives and biases. The wealth of introspective resources and writing from Braun and Clarke has helped shape our approach to qualitative analysis [4].

4.1 Methodology

This methodology somewhat contrasts the peer validated approach typical of research based on grounded theory [6]. In this study, one coder will analyse all transcripts while regularly meeting with the wider team to discuss the coding process and iteratively generate themes from the transcripts using the Nvivo software. The other authors are co-creators of XXX, who were present at the showings and met the participants and/or read some/all of the interview transcripts prior to engaging in the analysis sessions. This approach aims to ensure we are generating codes and themes that draw on the knowledge and experience of the research team [8]. In line with Clarke and Braun's process for reflexive thematic analysis, the approach for analysis follows the following steps:

1. Data familiarisation period for reviewers
2. Data coding using Nvivo software
3. Generation of themes
4. Discussion between researchers on themes, reflection and development
5. Iteration around steps 2-4

6. Refining and naming themes and developing of ideas around themes
7. Writing paper; discussion of themes

5 NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Removed For Peer Review

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